

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DETERMINATION OF PHYSICO-LITHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRODUCTIVE HORIZONS FOR DUAL COMPLETION OF WELLS

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Abstract

The article reflects a detailed analysis of the determination of the physico-lithological characteristics of productive horizons for dual completion (DC) at the Altyguyi deposit. This study is given for the DC of oil and gas with two elevators in one well. The article describes in detail the analyses carried out from the selected cores and slurries to determine the open porosity, density, granulometric composition, carbonateness, absolute permeability, residual water saturation, effective porosity, relative resistivity, as well as the determination of the average oil and gas saturation and filtration capacity indicators of silt-sand rocks. This work can be used to determine the heterogeneity of productive horizons for the development of multi-layer deposits by the DC method.

Keywords: core, permeability, porosity, water saturation, siltstone, core bit, incision.

Determination of the physico-lithological characteristics of rocks at the Altyguyi deposit was carried out by studying the section of 15 wells. 34 cores were obtained from the NK_{7d}, NK₈ and NK₉ horizons.

More than 320 rock samples were taken from the remaining productive horizons for laboratory studies. From these samples, analyses were carried out to determine the following physico-lithological characteristics of productive horizons;

- 298 samples for determination of open porosity and density;
- 327 samples for determination of granulometric composition and carbonate content;
- 53 samples to determine absolute permeability;
- 51 samples for determination of residual water saturation and effective porosity;
- 101 samples to determine the relative resistivity;

The complex of sedimentary rocks of the productive zone (horizons NK_{7g}, HK₈, HK₉) does not differ

from each other in lithology, they mainly consist of alternations of siltstone rocks with sandstones [1].

Clay in the section is about 1.6%.

Siltstones are widespread and make up about 78.8% and 18% sandstones.

Siltstone-sand productive sedimentary rocks of the Altyguyi deposit belong to an industrially productive reservoir and are characterized by more than 14% open porosity, more than 3-5 md permeability; no more than 45-50% water saturation.

In connection with the above, from the distribution of lithological indicators and a detailed analysis of the relationship between them, it makes it possible to divide siltstone-sand rock reservoirs into two types: industrial and non-industrial.

The conditioned values of reservoir and metophysical indicators of reservoirs of productive zones are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Conditioned values of collector and metaphysical indicators of collectors of productive zones

№	Indicators of collectors	Conditioned value	
		Types of collectors	
		industrial	not industrial
1	Open porosity, %	more 14	less than 14
2	Effective porosity, %	more 7-8	less than 7-8
3	Absolute permeability, md	more 3-5	less than 3-5
4	Carbonate content, %	less than 20	more 20
5	Clay, %	less than 28-30	more 30
6	Relative clay content, %	less than 0,55	more 0,55
7	Residual water saturation, %	less than 45	more 45

From the depth intervals of productive horizons, the penetration with core bits for the selection of cores of insufficient degree of removal is 31,3%. This can be explained by the fact that when the core is brought to the surface, there are weakly cemented and crumbly loose types of rocks in their composition. This is due to

the fact that such rocks are characterized by high K_p indicators, but the average permeability indicators according to core analyses may be slightly less important.

All types of the listed laboratory works are entirely given from the selected rock samples of 15 wells located in different places of the field [2].

Industrial accumulation of hydrocarbons accompanies the types of collectors of silt-sand rocks of the lower part of the red-colored strata of the NK_{7d}, NK₈ and NK₉ horizons. The horizon of NK₉, compared with the horizons of NK_{7d}, NK₈, has little information based on the core analysis materials.

The section of the productive zone consists of alternating weakly cemented rocks of some loose sandstones and clays, as well as strongly cemented siltstone rocks.

Basically, the layers of granular reservoirs with different capacities are located in the horizons of NK_{7d}

and NK₈. The values of the porosity coefficient K_p and the permeability coefficient K_{per} (granular reservoirs) vary in wide ranges [3].

The reservoir capacity of silt-sand rocks in the NK_{7d} horizon ranges from 14,1% to 21,5%, the permeability is 5-6 md. In the NK₈ horizon, the permeability changes to 210 md. The average porosity of industrial reservoirs for the NK_{7d} horizon is 18,3%, the NK₈ horizon is 17,8% and, respectively, the permeability is 71,4 md and 51,0 md. Tables 2,3 and 4 show the average values of filtration capacity and oil and gas saturation of silt-sand rocks.

Table 2

Average indicators of filtration-capacity and oil saturation of silt-sand rocks

Horizons	Open porosity, %		
	Average values	Number of definitions	Limit of change
NK _{7d}	18,3	39	14,1-21,5
NK ₈	17,8	19	16,9-19,7
NK ₉	-	-	-

Table 3

Average indicators of filtration-capacity and oil saturation of silt-sand rocks

Horizons	Absolute permeability, %		
	Average values	Number of definitions	Limit of change
NK _{7d}	71,4	25	13,0-210,0
NK ₈	51,0	18	5,6-87,1
NK ₉	-	-	-

Table 4

Average indicators of filtration-capacity and oil saturation of silt-sand rocks

Horizons	Oil and gas saturation, %		
	Average values	Number of definitions	Limit of change
NK _{7d}	66,4	24	60,7-78,6
NK ₈	62,6	18	57,0-69,0
NK ₉	-	-	-

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